

Legal Overview Human Genetics and Genomics: BRAZIL

[WP2 – Human Genetics and Genomics]

Lead contributor	Dr. Marcelo de Araujo – UFRJ marceloaraujo@direito.ufrj.br
Other contributors	Dr. Maria Clara Dias – UFRJ
Other contributors	Fabiana Pompermayer – UFRJ Doctoral Candidate in Bioethics & Health Policy
Reviewer	Amanda Olivo – Lawyer and Post-Graduate Student in Philosophy at the State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ)
Due date	30 November 2018
Delivery date	29 March 2019
Type	Report
Dissemination level	PU = Public
Keywords	Legal analysis, human genetics, genomics, genetic testing, genetic screening, gene editing

The SIENNA project - *Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact* - has received funding under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741716.

© SIENNA, 2019

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Executive Summary

In this report, the Brazilian regulatory framework for human genomics and human genetics is analysed. The regulatory framework examined in this report consists of legislation enacted by the Brazilian government, Bills for the creation of new legislation, and legislation that apply only within a specific state of the Brazilian Federation, or only within a specific municipality. The report also examines “Resolutions” issued by bodies of the government that do not have legislative power, but whose decisions are binding within a specific area. The report focuses on three specific bodies of the government, to wit the Brazilian Health Regulatory Agency, or ANVISA (*Port.: Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária*); the Federal Medical Council, or CFM (*Conselho Federal de Medicina*); and the National Technical Board on Biosecurity, or CTNBio (*Port.: Comissão Técnica Nacional de Biossegurança*).

The report consists of two parts. Part I provides a discussion of relevant legal developments and a summary of relevant academic literature on the topic under consideration. Part II addresses specific legal issues concerning gene editing, genetic testing, genetic screening, newborn screening, advertising of genetic services (genetic testing and genetic screening), and biobanking. We endeavoured to survey the relevant legal literature for every topic addressed in this report, but we have realised that the broad societal implications of human genomics and human genetics have been examined by sociologists, philosophers, and historians rather than legal scholars.

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Reason for change	Distribution
V1	1 November 2018	First Draft	Further work on the report	Task leaders
V2	30 November	Final Version	Feedback from reviewers	Task leaders

Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
Task 2.2	This report is part of and, will provide input to deliverable 2.2.
This 4.2	This report will provide input to deliverable 4.2.

Table of contents

List of tables.....	5
Table 1 List of acronyms/abbreviations	5
Table 2 Glossary of terms.....	5
Part I	8
1. National legal system in context	8
1.1 An overview of Brazil’s legal system	8
1.2 Brazil and United Nations.....	9
1.3 Brazil and UNESCO	9
1.4 Brazil and OECD	9
1.5 Brazil and OAS.....	10
2. Objectives of the report.....	10
3. Approach, materials and method.....	10
3.1 Literature overview	10
3.2 Legal developments	10
3.3 Analysis of legislation	10
4. Scope and limitations of the report	11
Part II	11
5. Current legal developments and legal academic debates in the area of genetics and genomics	11
5.1 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding human germline gene editing	11
5.2 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding genetic screening in general.....	12
5.3 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding genetic testing in general	13
5.4 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding prenatal testing/screening	14
5.5 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding newborn screening	15
5.6 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening	15
Part III Specific legal considerations on human genetics and genomics	16
7. Human germline gene editing.....	16
8. Genetic screening in general.....	19
9. Genetic testing in general.....	20

10. Prenatal testing/screening 23

11. Newborn screening..... 24

12. Advertising of genetic testing or screening..... 25

13. Biobanks 28

Part IV Discussion and conclusions..... 30

14. Discussion 30

15. Conclusion 30

References 31

List of tables

- **Table 1:** List of acronyms/abbreviations
- **Table 2:** Glossary of terms

Table 1 List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ANVISA	Brazilian Health Regulatory Agency (<i>Port.:</i> <i>Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária</i>) http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/
CFM	Federal Medical Council (<i>Conselho Federal de Medicina</i>) https://portal.cfm.org.br/
CTNBio	National Technical Board on Biosecurity (<i>Port.:</i> <i>Comissão Técnica Nacional de Biossegurança, CTNBio</i>) http://ctnbio.mcti.gov.br/inicio
DTC	Direct-to-consumer
GT	Genetic testing
Port.	Portuguese language
SUS	Unified Health Care System (<i>Port.:</i> <i>Sistema Único de Saúde</i>) http://portalms.saude.gov.br/sistema-unico-de-saude

Table 2 Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Genetic Test	A genetic test: is an assay performed to obtain genetic information (directly on DNA or even on other molecules (RNA, proteins), which by extension could give us genetic information.
Genetic Testing	Genetic testing is usually offered to individual patients based on specific individual need on a one-on-one basis (diagnostic testing, prenatal testing, etc. https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/uses). An assay (a genetic test) would be conducted after the clinician has decided to prescribe the test to the specific patient in question. Genetic testing is a type of medical test that identifies changes in chromosomes, genes, or proteins. The results of a genetic test can confirm or rule out a suspected genetic condition or help determine a person's chance of developing or passing on a genetic disorder. ¹ Genetic

¹ US National Library of Medicine, Genetic Home Reference, What is genetic testing?
<https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/genetic-testing>

	<p>testing could be accessed through a health care provider as part of clinical medical care, or as a service or product offered directly to consumers. Issues genetic testing raises relate to access rights, protection of integrity, medical oversight when these tests are being offered, as well as genetic counselling, and quality.</p> <p>Other questions that relate to genetic testing emerge in the area of advertising and the use of genetic information. In regard to advertising such issues as, for example, whether genetic testing providers are or are not allowed to advertise their offered genetic tests emerge (contrast with a distinction being made for advertising prescription and non-prescription drugs).² In regard to genetic information, such issues as who can access one’s genetic information, and how this information could be used for different purposes, for example, life insurance. One of key issues that emerges in this regard is discrimination relating to one’s genome.</p>
<p>Genetic Screening</p>	<p>Genetic screening can have a few different meanings that differ based on subtle nuances and contexts, but in general, we contrast genetic screening from genetic testing because screening is offered to an entire group of people (not specific individuals). In particular screening cases, like newborn screening, for example, the screening programme follows public health frameworks (as opposed to genetic testing which is not a public health programme but within a clinical specialty; in countries where public health programmes don’t differ so strongly from clinical practice, you may want to ignore this if it confuses you more. Differences between public health programmes and clinical (one patient at a time) programmes could mean differences in how we approach consent and the obligatory nature of any programme). Other than the “group/population” aim of screening programmes, screening programmes can vary hugely in different ways: population/group targeted (population wide? Certain people/mothers at higher risks as a group?) etc.</p>
<p>Gene Editing/Genome Editing</p>	<p>Gene editing is a relatively recent term used for the description of modifying DNA (you may have previously heard in the past recombinant DNA technology or similar terms that all overlap in some fashion); the term gene editing has come along with the advent of particularly powerful and accurate tools like CRISPR-Cas9 (which is a tool that helps to change DNA). Gene editing can also be referred to as genome modification, which is more holistic, if you will as a concept, but addresses the same ideas; it basically includes not only changing individual DNA in one location but also many changes throughout the genome. One can edit genes in somatic cells (which are not inherited) or one could edit genes in gametes or germline cells which are inherited and would pass down, in theory, DNA modifications/edits to future</p>

² Please consult Louiza Kalokairinou and Pascal Borry and Heidi Carmen Howard, “Regulating the advertising of genetic tests in Europe: a balancing act”, *Journal of Medical Genetics*, Volume 54, Issue 10.

	<p>generations.</p> <p>The term human genome germline modification then includes the modification of 1 or many bits of DNA in an inheritable human cell. Many authors also include the replacement of mitochondria from one embryo to another as a type of germline modification, though this can be argued as (not) being very distinct from DNA modification, for the sake of comparison with other studies, we will include it for the purposes of this SIENNA study.</p>
“Projeto de Lei”	Refers to legislative Bill in Portuguese

Part I

1. National legal system in context

1.1 An overview of Brazil's legal system

Brazil is a federative republic that encompasses 26 states, and 1 Federal District³, with a population of ca. 210 million inhabitants. Each state contains a number of municipalities. Brazil currently has 5.570 municipalities. The municipalities, within the states, and the states, within the federation as a whole, have a degree of autonomy to produce laws, regulations, amendments, and decrees. But all normative acts issued by states and by the municipalities must ultimately accord with the 1988 Federal Constitution (henceforth simply Constitution). The Constitution provides the legal framework for the enactment of laws, decrees, regulations, and amendments both at a federal level and at the level of the states and municipalities. The Constitution also contains instructions for the enactment of provisional measures, which are issued by the President of the Republic in exceptional and urgent situations. Provisional measures have force of law, but only for a limited period of time. After being examined by the National Congress, the provisional measures are converted into ordinary laws, if approved. If rejected, they lose effectiveness and the National Congress must regulate the matter.

The Judiciary Branch is divided into Federal Judiciary and State Judiciary. The Federal Judiciary is composed by the Supreme Federal Court (STF), Superior Court of Justice (STJ), Federal Regional Courts (TRFs) and the Federal Court. There are also specialized courts that deal with electoral, labour and military matters. The Brazilian legislative process generally begins with a bill (*Port.: projeto de lei*) in one of the Houses of Congress, namely the Chamber of Deputies (the Lower House) and the Federal Senate (the Upper House). The bill is either approved or rejected by voting. After a bill has been approved by both Houses (the Chamber of Deputies and the Federal Senate), it is sent to the President of the Republic to be sanctioned or vetoed, in its totality or only in part.

The most important piece of legislation for research with living organisms in Brazil is the Federal Law No. 11.105, from 24 March 2005, also known as the Biosecurity Law (*Port.: Lei de Biosegurança*, henceforth simply "Biosecurity Law").⁴ The Biosecurity Law established the National Council of Biosecurity (*Port.: Conselho Nacional de Biossegurança, CNBS*) and remodelled the National Technical Board on Biosecurity (*Port.: Comissão Técnica Nacional de Biossegurança, CTNBio*):

³ The Federal District (*Port.: Distrito Federal*) is a federal territory formed by the capital city, Brasília, and satellite-cities that function as a regional administrative area. The Federal District has a differentiated status in the federation, with features both of states and of municipalities.

⁴ Brasil, "Lei No. 11.105", 24 March 2005.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_Ato2004-2006/2005/Lei/L11105.htm

CTNBio is a multidisciplinary collegiate body, created by Law No. 11.105, from 24 March 2005, whose purpose is to provide technical advisory support and advice to the Federal Government in the formulation, updating and implementation of the National Biosafety Policy on GMOs such as establishing technical safety standards and technical advice on the protection of human health, living organisms and the environment for activities involving the construction, testing, cultivation, handling, transport, marketing, consumption, storage, release and disposal of GMOs and derivatives.⁵

The Biosecurity Law, along with the rules established by the CNBS and CTNBio, provide the main legal and regulatory framework for research in genomics and genetics in Brazil.

1.2 Brazil and United Nations

Brazil ranks among the founding members of the United Nations. As of 2016, Brazil was the 6th largest contributor to the United Nations' budget. Brazil also participates in all specialized agencies of the United Nations.⁶ In 2005, Brazil voted against the (non-binding) "United Nations Declaration on Human Cloning". The declaration aimed at the adoption of "all measures necessary to prohibit all forms of human cloning inasmuch as they are incompatible with human dignity and the protection of human life."⁷

1.3 Brazil and UNESCO

Brazil is a signatory of the UNESCO "International Declaration on Human Genetic Data", from October 2003, and the "Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights", from November 1997.⁸ According to the Brazilian Supreme Court, Brazil adopts a moderate dualist model of domestic and international law. These two UNESCO declarations have not yet been formally incorporated into the Brazilian internal body of national legislation, as required by the Constitution.

1.4 Brazil and OECD

Currently, Brazil is not a member of the OECD. Its proposed membership is under consideration.⁹

⁵ Brasil (Ministério da Ciência Tecnologia e Inovação, Comissão Técnica Nacional de Biossegurança, CNTBio: <http://ctnbio.mcti.gov.br>

⁶ Dubbudu, Rakesh, "How much do various countries contribute to the UN Budget?", *Factly*, 13 December 2016. <https://factly.in/united-nations-budget-contributions-by-member-countries/>

⁷ United Nation, "General assembly adopts United Nations Declaration on Human Cloning by vote of 84-34-37", *Press Release*, 8 March 2005. <https://www.un.org/press/en/2005/ga10333.doc.htm>

⁸ UNESCO, "International Declaration on Human Genetic Data", 16 October 2003. <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genetic-data/>
UNESCO, "Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights", 11 November 1997. <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genome-and-human-rights/>

⁹ Reuters, "Brazil is seeking to join the OECD despite its political crisis", *Fortune*, 31 May 2017. <http://fortune.com/2017/05/30/brazil-oecd-membership-temer/>

1.5 Brazil and OAS

Brazil is a member of the Organization of American States (OAS). It is a signatory of the “Inter-American Convention against All Forms of Discrimination and Intolerance”, including discrimination and intolerance related to “genetic traits”.¹⁰

2. Objectives of the report

The report provides an examination of the regulatory framework for human genetics and human genomics in Brazil. It focuses on laws enacted by the government, Bills proposed by the government, and Resolutions issued – by bodies of the government (ANVISA, CFM, and CTNBio) whose decisions are relevant for human genomics and human genetics.

Part I of this report provides a discussion of relevant legal developments and a summary of relevant academic literature on the topic under consideration. Part II addresses specific legal issues concerning gene editing, genetic testing, genetic screening, newborn screening, advertising of genetic services (genetic testing and genetic screening), and biobanking.

3. Approach, materials and method

3.1 Literature overview

We made every effort to survey the relevant legal scholarship for every topic addressed in this report. Yet, the societal implications of human genomics and human genetics in Brazil seem to have been examined thus far by sociologists, philosophers, and historians rather than legal scholars. We use the broader term “academic literature” to refer to scholarly works that cover topics that are relevant for an examination of the Brazilian framework for human genomics and human genetics, but which do not necessarily have been published by legal scholars.

3.2 Legal developments

The report, as stated above, focuses on legislation enacted by the government, on current Bills proposed by the government, and on some Resolutions issued by regulatory bodies such as ANVISA, CFM, and CTNBio.

3.3 Analysis of legislation

Whenever possible, the report calls attention to legislations that apply for genetic services offered by the government as opposed to services that are offered only in the private sector. Some services that, currently, are available only in the private sector are under consideration to be offered, in the future, in public health care system too (also known as SUS). The report, then, calls attention to the most relevant government Bills in this regard.

¹⁰ Organization of American States (OAS), “Inter-American Convention against All Forms of Discrimination and Intolerance”, *Department of International Law (DIL)*, 2013.

http://www.oas.org/en/sla/dil/inter_american_treaties_A-69_discrimination_intolerance.asp

4. Scope and limitations of the report

As stated above, Brazil is a federative republic with 26 states, 1 Federal District, and 5.570 municipalities. States and municipalities have a degree of autonomy to enact laws and to regulate services that, sometimes, are not available in the national public health care system as a whole, but only in some states or some municipalities. The genetic test to detect the mutation of the *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes, for instance, is currently available only in the public health care system of a few states. Inhabitants of states where the test is not available for free have to resort to the private sector. In this report we focus on government legislation and government Bills. There has been no attempt to survey the peculiarities of legislation and proposed Bills that pertain to specific states, or to specific municipalities.¹¹

Part II

5. Current legal developments and legal academic debates in the area of genetics and genomics

5.1 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding human germline gene editing

In spite of some recent legal debates and legal developments for the use of CRISPR-Cas9 in the agriculture and farming¹² there have not been legal developments or legal debates concerning the use of gene editing technologies in human genetics and human genomics.

Main regulatory frameworks for the use of biotechnology in plants, human, and non-human animals

Brasil, “Lei No. 11.105”, 24 March 2005.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_Ato2004-2006/2005/Lei/L11105.htm

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Resolução Nº 466, 12 November 2012”

<http://conselho.saude.gov.br/resolucoes/2012/Reso466.pdf>

¹¹ For an extensive list of Bills related to human genetics and human genomics proposed at state and municipal levels, see Projeto Ghente, “Documentos jurídicos”, *Projeto Ghente*, http://www.ghente.org/doc_juridicos/

¹² Silveira, Evanildo, “Os genes do gado”, *Pesquisa FAPESP*, April 2017.

<http://revistapesquisa.fapesp.br/2017/04/19/os-genes-do-gado/>

See also Colussi, Joana, “Edição de Gene e DNA em plantas e animais pode revolucionar o campo”, *Campo e Lavoura*, 8 June 2018.

<https://gauchazh.clicrbs.com.br/economia/campo-e-lavoura/noticia/2018/06/edicao-de-dna-em-plantas-e-animais-promete-revolucionar-o-campo-cji69j8my0etc01qo8vhjwe04.html>

Main regulatory frameworks for research with non-human animals

Brasil, Presidência da República, “Decreto No. 6.899”, 15 July 2009.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_Ato2007-2010/2009/Decreto/D6899.htm

Brasil, “Lei No. 11.794”, 8 Outubro 2008.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2007-2010/2008/lei/l11794.htm

Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Guia para a Condução de Estudos Não Clínicos de Toxicologia e Segurança Farmacológica Necessários ao Desenvolvimento de Medicamentos - Versão 2 (Versão 1.1)”, 31 January 2013.

http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/resultado-de-busca?p_p_id=101&p_p_lifecycle=0&p_p_state=maximized&p_p_mode=view&p_p_col_id=column-1&p_p_col_count=1&_101_struts_action=%2Fasset_publisher%2Fview_content&_101_assetEntryId=3274317&_101_type=document

Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Nota da Anvisa sobre o uso de animais em estudos pré-clínicos” ASCOM, 24 January 2013.

http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/noticias/-/asset_publisher/FXrpx9qY7FbU/content/nota-da-anvisa-sobre-o-uso-de-animais-em-estudos-pre-clinicos/219201/pop_up?inheritRedirect=false

The ethical implications of gene editing technologies have been addressed by some authors from a philosophical perspective.¹³ On the other hand, we have not been able to find legal scholarship on this topic.

5.2 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding genetic screening in general

This law regulates the activities of the Brazilian Unified Health Care System (Port.: Sistema Único de Saúde)

Brasil, “Lei No. 8.080”, September 1990.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/L8080.htm

This law regulates the activities of the National Newborn Screening Initiative (Port.: Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal, PNTN), which are pursued within the SUS

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 822”, 06 June 2001.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2001/prt0822_06_06_2001.html

This law regulates the activities of the National Policy for Comprehensive Care in Clinical Genetics (Port.: Política Nacional de Atenção Integral em Genética Clínica)

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 81”, 20 January 2009.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2009/prt0081_20_01_2009.html

¹³ See for instance Araujo, Marcelo de, “Editing the genome of human beings CRISPR-Cas9 and the ethics of genetic enhancement”. *Journal of Evolution and Technology*, Vol. 27, No. 1, 2017, pp. 24-42.

This law regulates the activities of the National Policy for Integral Care concerning People with Rare Diseases (Port.: Política Nacional de Atenção Integral às Pessoas com Doenças Raras).

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 199”, 30 January 2014.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2014/prt0199_30_01_2014.html

This document establishes guidelines for the treatment of persons with rare genetic diseases

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Diretrizes para Atenção Integral às Pessoas com Doenças Raras no Sistema Único de Saúde – SUS”, Brasília, 2014.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/diretrizes_atencao_integral_pessoa_doencas_raras_SUS.pdf

Academic literature

Löwy, Ilana, “Visible Disasters: Fetopathology in Brazil”, in *Tangled Diagnoses: Prenatal Testing, Women, and Risk*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London, 2018, pp. 116.

Horovitz, Dafne Dain Gandelman, and Antonia Paula Marques-de-Faria, and Victor Evangelista de Faria Ferraz, “The practice of medical genetics in Brazil”, in Dhavendra Kumar (ed.), *Genomics and Health in the Developing World*. Oxford University Press, 2012, pp. 1224.

We have not been able to find legal scholarship on genetic screening in general.

5.3 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding genetic testing in general

Government Bill (Port.: projeto de lei) for the introduction of genetic tests to detect the mutation of the BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes within the public health care system

Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 6262”, 12 September 2013.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao;jsessionid=1DD9D9A22918DDE3711C1E4078D7878B.node2?idProposicao=590549&ord=0>

This law introduced genetic tests to detect the mutation of the BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes within the public health care system of the state of Rio de Janeiro

Rio de Janeiro (Assembléia Legislativa Rio de Janeiro), “Lei No. 7049”, 25 August 2015.

<http://alerjln1.alerj.rj.gov.br/CONTLEI.NSF/e9589b9aabd9cac8032564fe0065abb4/b598c5bdbbe2dc83257ead006ff9fe?OpenDocument>

Government Bill for the introduction of genetic counselling within the public health care system

Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 1971”, 17 September 2007.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=366398>

This resolution issued by the Brazilian Federal Medical Council (Conselho Federal de Medicina) establishes rules for the use of IVF and PGD in fertility clinics

Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No.2.168”, 2017.

<https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2168>

Academic literature

Hochman, Gilberto, and Nísia Trindade Lima, Macos Chor Maio, “The path of eugenics in Brazil: Dilemmas of miscegenation”, in Alison Bashford, Philippa Levine (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of the History of Eugenics*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2010, pp. 493-510.

Mendes, Marcela Custodio and Ana Paula Pimentel Costa, “Diagnóstico genético pré-implantacional: prevenção, tratamento de doenças genéticas e aspectos etico-legais”, *Revista Ciências Médicas e Biológica*, Salvador, Vol. 12, n.3, September/December, 2013, pp.374-379.
https://repositorio.ufba.br/ri/bitstream/ri/23102/1/17_v.12_3.pdf

Passos-Bueno, Maria Rita et al. “Genetics and genomics in Brazil: a promising future”, *Molecular Genetics & Genomic Medicine*, Vol. 2, No. 4, 2014, pp. 280-91.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4113268/>

Stepan, Nancy Leys, “Eugenics in Brazil, 1917-1940”, in Mark B. Adams (ed.), *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia*, Oxford University Press, Oxford/New York, 1990, pp. 110-152.

Walsh, Sarah, “The executioner’s shadow: Coerced sterilization and the creation of ‘Latin’ eugenics in Chile”, *History of Science*, pp. 1-23 (doi/10.1177/0073275318755533).

We have not been able to find legal scholarship on genetic testing in general.

5.4 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding prenatal testing/screening

This law regulated pre-natal care within the public health care system

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 569”, 1 June 2000.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2000/prt0569_01_06_2000_rep.html

Government Bill for the introduction of genetic counselling within the public health care system

Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 1971”, 17 September 2007.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=366398>

The Brazilian Civil Code (Brazilian Private law Main Statute)

Brasil, “Código Civil Brasileiro. Lei No. 10.406”, 10 January 2002.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/l10406.htm

This resolution issued by the Brazilian Federal Medical Council (Conselho Federal de Medicina) establishes rules for the use of IVF and PGD in fertility clinics

Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No. 2.168”, 2017.

<https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2168>

Academic literature

Mendes, Marcela Custodio and Ana Paula Pimentel Costa, “Diagnóstico genético pré-implantacional: prevenção, tratamento de doenças genéticas e aspectos etico-legais”, *Revista Ciências Médicas e*

Biológica, Salvador, Vol. 12, n.3, September/December 2013, pp.374-379.

https://repositorio.ufba.br/ri/bitstream/ri/23102/1/17_v.12_3.pdf

We have not been able to find legal scholarship on prenatal testing/screening.

5.5 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding newborn screening

This law regulates the activities of the National Newborn Screening Initiative (Port.: Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal, PNTN), which are pursued within the SUS

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 822”, June 2001.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2001/prt0822_06_06_2001.html

This law establishes Guidelines for Attention to Neonatal Hearing Screening (Port.: Diretrizes de Atenção à Triagem Auditiva Neonatal) within the SUS

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 1.328”, 3 December 2012.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/sas/2012/prt1328_03_12_2012.html

Guidelines for Attention to Neonatal Hearing Screening (Port.: Diretrizes de Atenção à Triagem Auditiva Neonatal) within the SUS

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), *Diretrizes da Atenção à Triagem Auditiva Neonatal*, Brasília, 2012.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/diretrizes_atencao_triagem_auditiva_neonatal.pdf

This 92-page document, issued by the Brazilian Ministry of Health, contains operational guidelines for newborn screening

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), *Manual de Normas Técnicas e Rotinas Operacionais do Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal*, 2002.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/triagem_neonatal.pdf

Government Bill for the introduction of further genetic tests in current newborn screening program

Brasil, “Projeto de Lei 6771”, 24 August 2017.

http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/prop_mostrarintegra?codteor=1519297

Academic literature

Leão, Leticia Lima and Marcos José Aguiar, “Triagem neonatal: o que os pediatras deveriam saber”, *J. Pediatr. (Rio J.)*, Vol. 84, n.4, suppl., 2008, pp.S80-S90. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0021-75572008000500012>

We have not been able to find legal scholarship on newborn screening.

5.6 Current legal developments and legal academic debates regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening

Brazilian Consumer Protection Code

Brasil, “Lei No. 8.078”, 11 September 1990.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

Brazilian Civil Code (Brazilian Private law Main Statute)

Brasil, “Código Civil Brasileiro, Lei No. 10.406”, 10 January 2002.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/l10406.htm

This resolution issued by the Brazilian Federal Medical Council (Conselho Federal de Medicina) establishes rules for the use of IVF and PGD in fertility clinics

Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM). Resolução CFM No.2.168/2017.

<https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2168>

Academic literature

Mendes, Marcela Custodio and Ana Paula Pimentel Costa, “Diagnóstico genético pré-implantacional: prevenção, tratamento de doenças genéticas e aspectos etico-legais”, *Revista Ciências Médicas e Biológica*, Salvador, Vol. 12, No.3, September/December, 2013, pp. 374-379.

https://repositorio.ufba.br/ri/bitstream/ri/23102/1/17_v.12_3.pdf

We have not been able to find legal scholarship on advertising of genetic testing or screening.

Part III Specific legal considerations on human genetics and genomics

7. Human germline gene editing

7.1. The Biosecurity Law clearly prohibits human germline gene editing:

Art. 6. It is prohibited:

[...]

II – genetic engineering in the living organism or in vitro manipulation of natural or recombinant DNA / RNA, carried out in disagreement with the norms established in this Law;

III – genetic engineering in human germ cell, human zygote and human embryo;

IV – human cloning

On the other hand, the Biosecurity Law does permit some basic research with human cells, as stated in Art. 5:

Article 5. The use of embryonic stem cells obtained from human embryos produced by in vitro fertilization and not used in the respective procedure is allowed, for the purposes of research and therapy, subject to the following conditions:

- They are non-viable embryos, or

- The embryos have been frozen for three (3) years or more, as of the date of publication of this Law, or frozen since the date of publication of this Law, after completing 3 (three) years from the date of freezing.
- § 1 In any case, the consent of the parents is required.
- § 2o Research institutions and health services that perform research or therapy with human embryonic stem cells should submit their projects to the appreciation and approval of the respective research ethics committees.

Paragraph 3 - The commercialization of the biological material referred to in this article is prohibited and its practice implies the crime typified in art. 15 of Law No. 9.434 of February 4, 1997.

Although the word “research” (*Port.: pesquisa*) occurs 20 times throughout the text of the Biosecurity Law, the word does not occur in conjunction with the word “basic”. The Biosecurity Law does not provide a definition of “basic research”. On the other hand, “basic research” (*Port.: pesquisa básica*) does appear in another legal document, namely in the Federal Decree No. 5.798, from 7 June 2006¹⁴, which regulates Law No. 11.196, from 21 November 2005, also known as “Benefit Law” (*Port.: Lei do Bem*).¹⁵ This law creates tax incentives for private companies that invest in Research and Development (R&D). Decree No. 5.798 defines different kinds of research in Art. 2, II:

- [...] a) basic directed research: the works executed with the objective of acquiring knowledge relative to the understanding of new phenomena, with a view to the development of innovative products, processes or systems;
- b) applied research: the works carried out with the objective of acquiring new knowledge, with a view to the development or improvement of products, processes and systems; [...]

Another government document explains that the concepts of “R&D” and “research”, including “basic research”, that underlie both the Benefit Law and Decree No. 5.798 ultimately rely on the definition of “basic research” provided by the Frascati Manual.¹⁶

7.2. The Biosecurity Law does not prohibit the use of gene editing technologies in non-human cells. Gene editing technologies have recently been used, for instance, to enhance the quality of cattle

¹⁴ Brasil, “Decreto No. 5.798”, 7 June 2006.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ Ato2004-2006/2006/Decreto/D5798.htm

¹⁵ Brasil, “Lei No. 11.196”, 21 November 2005. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ ato2004-2006/2005/lei/l11196.htm

¹⁶ Brasil (Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação).

https://www.mctic.gov.br/mctic/opencms/perguntas_frequentes/Lei_do_Bem.html

See also “O que é a Lei do Bem?” <https://www.leidobem.com/manual-de-frascati/>.

See also Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). “Frascati Manual”.

<http://www.oecd.org/innovation/inno/frascati-manual.htm>.

production in Brazil.¹⁷ And the British company Oxitec has been granted permission to produce genetically modified *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes in Brazil in order to fight diseases such as dengue and chikungunya, which are transmitted by *Aedes aegypti* mosquito.¹⁸

The Brazilian Health Regulatory Agency (ANVISA, *Port.: Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária*), which is the official body of the government responsible for the assessment of the efficacy and safety of medicines or health products aiming at the Brazilian market, defines “clinical research” (*Port.: pesquisa clínica*) as follows:

Clinical research are studies carried out on human beings to measure the safety and efficacy parameters of new drugs and is essential for the arrival of new therapeutic alternatives in the market. These trials are divided into phases I, II, III and IV, according to the number of participants and the specific objectives of each step.¹⁹

ANVISA draws a distinction between preclinical and clinical research as follows:

In preclinical (animal experiments) and clinical (human-test) studies, data are produced on the effects, limits and safe conditions of use of the products used for the diagnosis, treatment or prophylaxis of diseases.²⁰

¹⁷ Silveira, Evanildo, “Os genes do gado”, *Pesquisa FAPESP*, No. 254, April 2017.

<http://revistapesquisa.fapesp.br/2017/04/19/os-genes-do-gado/>

See also Colussi, Joana, “Edição de gene e DNA em plantas e animais pode revolucionar o campo”, *Campo e Lavoura*, 8 June 2018. <https://gauchazh.clicrbs.com.br/economia/campo-e-lavoura/noticia/2018/06/edicao-de-dna-em-plantas-e-animais-promete-revolucionar-o-campo-cji69j8my0etc01qo8vhjwe04.html>

¹⁸ Martins, Helena, “Justiça autoriza empresa a comercializar *Aedes aegypti* modificado”, *Agência Brasil*, 23 March 2018.

<http://agenciabrasil.ebc.com.br/pesquisa-e-inovacao/noticia/2018-03/justica-autoriza-empresa-comercializar-aedes-aegypti-modificado>. See also Servick, Kelly, “Brazil will release billions of lab-grown mosquitoes to combat infectious disease. Will it work?”, *Science*, 13 October 2016.

<http://www.sciencemag.org/news/2016/10/brazil-will-release-billions-lab-grown-mosquitoes-combat-infectious-disease-will-it> See also Moraes, Fernando Tadeu, “Justiça autoriza Oxitec a comercializar mosquito transgênico”, *Folha de São Paulo*, 26 March 2018. <https://www1.folha.uol.com.br/ciencia/2018/03/justica-autoriza-oxitec-a-comercializar-mosquito-transgenico.shtml>. See also OXITEC. <http://br.oxitec.com/>

¹⁹ Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Regularização de Empresas: Medicamentos, Pesquisa Clínica”. <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/pesquisa-clinica>

See also: Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Resolução da Diretoria Colegiada - RDC No. 10”, 3 March 2015. http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/documents/10181/3503972/RDC_10_2015_.pdf/9ecdac85-1b8e-4f69-9a69-996de4386244

²⁰ Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Nota da Anvisa sobre o uso de animais em estudos pré-clínicos”, 24 January 2013. http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/noticias/-/asset_publisher/FXrpx9qY7FbU/content/nota-da-anvisa-sobre-o-uso-de-animais-em-estudos-pre-clinicos/219201/pop_up?inheritRedirect=false

See also Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Guia para a Condução de Estudos Não Clínicos de Toxicologia e Segurança Farmacológica Necessários ao Desenvolvimento de Medicamentos - Versão 2 (Versão 1.1)”, 31 January 2013. http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/resultado-de-busca?p_p_id=101&p_p_lifecycle=0&p_p_state=maximized&p_p_mode=view&p_p_col_id=column-1&p_p_col_count=1&_101_struts.action=%2Fasset_publisher%2Fview_content&_101_assetEntryId=3274317&_101_type=document

According to ANVISA, pre-clinical research with animals must be carried out in line with Law No. 11.794, from 8 October 2008 (also known as “Lei Arouca”) and also in accordance with the resolutions issued by the National Council for the Control of Animal Experimentation (*Port.:* CONCEA, *Conselho Nacional de Controle de Experimentação Animal*).²¹ Research projects that involve the genetic modification of non-human animal must be carried out in line with Law No. 11.794 and in accordance with Decree No. 6.899, from 15 July 2009,²² and comply with the rules established by CTNBio.

7.3. and 7.4. As stated above, the Biosecurity Law (Art. 6) prohibits the use of germline modification technologies in human cells. To the best of our knowledge, there has not been in a Brazil a broad public debate, or legal parliamentary discussion, to amend the Biosecurity Law so as to make the use of gene editing technologies in human cells legally acceptable.

8. Genetic screening in general

According to the Brazilian 1988 Constitution,²³ every citizen has a basic right to health. In order to guarantee the protection of this right, Brazilian government created in 1990 the Unified Health Care System (*Port.:* *Sistema Único de Saúde, SUS*), which provides diagnoses and treatment free of charge to the population.²⁴ SUS is reported to have taken the British NHS (National Health Service) as a model.²⁵ The quality of health services provided by SUS can substantially vary from state to state and, ultimately, from municipality to municipality, mainly due to unequal distribution of material resources and human expertise throughout the country.

²¹ Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Nota da Anvisa sobre o uso de animais em estudos pré-clínicos”, 24 January 2013. http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/noticias/-/asset_publisher/FXrpx9qY7FbU/content/nota-da-anvisa-sobre-o-uso-de-animais-em-estudos-pre-clinicos/219201/pop_up?inheritRedirect=false

See also Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Guia para a Condução de Estudos Não Clínicos de Toxicologia e Segurança Farmacológica Necessários ao Desenvolvimento de Medicamentos - Versão 2 (Versão 1.1)”, 31 January 2013. See also Brasil, “Lei No. 11.794”, 8 October 2008.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2007-2010/2008/lei/l11794.htm

See also Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, “Bem-estar deve reger a experimentação animal, afirma coordenadora do Concea”, 14 August 2018.

<https://www.mctic.gov.br/mctic/opencms/institucional/concea/index.html>

See also Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, Legislação do CONCEA, “Lei 11.794”, 8 October 2008.

<https://www.mctic.gov.br/mctic/opencms/institucional/concea/paginas/legislacao.html>

²² Brasil, “Decreto No. 6.899”, 15 July 2009. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2007-2010/2009/Decreto/D6899.htm

²³ Brasil, “Constituição da República Federativa do Brasil”.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm

²⁴ Brasil, “Lei No. 8.080”, 19 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/L8080.htm

²⁵ Tanaka, Oswaldo Yoshimi and Vanessa Elias de Oliveira, “Reforma(s) e Estruturação do Sistema de Saúde Britânico: lições para o SUS”, *Saúde e Sociedade*, Vol. 16, No. 1, April 2007, pp. 7-17.

<http://www.scielo.br/pdf/sausoc/v16n1/02.pdf>. See also, Fundação Oswaldo Cruz, “Os sistemas de saúde pública brasileiro e inglês enfrentam dilemas no ano em que completam 30 e 70 anos”, *Centro de Estudos Estratégicos da Fiocruz*, 21 February 2018. <http://www.cee.fiocruz.br/?q=os-sistemas-de-saude-publica-brasileiro-e-ingles-enfrentam-dilemas-no-ano-em-que-completam-30-e-70-anos>

Brazilian government created in 2001 the National Newborn Screening Initiative (*Port.: Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal, PNTN*) by means of Decree No. 822, from 6 July 2001.²⁶ PNTN operates within the SUS and is the most extensive genetic screening program in Brazil. SUS did not originally have a comprehensive health policy for genetic screening at large. Lack of regulation in this area led the government, then, to create a Working Group for Clinical Genetics (*Port.: Grupo de Trabalho de Genética Clínica*) by means of Decree (*Port.: Portaria*) No. 2.380, from 28 October 2004.²⁷ Five years later the National Policy for Comprehensive Care in Clinical Genetics (*Port.: Política Nacional de Atenção Integral em Genética Clínica*) was established by means of Decree No. 81, from 20 January 2009.²⁸ A new decree (No. 199, from 30 January 2014) established later the National Policy for Integral Care concerning People with Rare Diseases (*Port.: Política Nacional de Atenção Integral às Pessoas com Doenças Raras, aprova as Diretrizes para Atenção Integral às Pessoas com Doenças Raras no âmbito do Sistema Único de Saúde (SUS)*).²⁹ Currently, though, there are no official figures about the number or types of genetic tests performed in Brazil.³⁰

9. Genetic testing in general

Genetic testing (*Port.: teste genético* or *exame genético*), as opposed to genetic screening (*Port.: triagem genética*, or less frequently *rastreamento genético*), is offered in Brazil both by the public and by the private sector. As far as the public sector is concerned, in addition to the heel prick test, which falls under the category of genetic screening and is mandatory in Brazil, the government also offers (or intends to offer, as the case may be) a range of optional genetic tests for individuals under

²⁶ Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 822”, 06 June 2001.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2001/prt0822_06_06_2001.html

See also: Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Dados sobre o Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal”, 28 June 2017.

<http://portalms.saude.gov.br/acoes-e-programas/programa-nacional-da-triagem-neonatal/dados-sobre-o-programa-nacional-de-triagem-neonatal>

See also Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), *Manual de Normas Técnicas e Rotinas Operacionais do Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal*, 2002. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/triagem_neonatal.pdf

²⁷ Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 2.380”, 28 October 2004.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2004/prt2380_28_10_2004.html

²⁸ Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 81”, 20 January 2009.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2009/prt0081_20_01_2009.html

²⁹ Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 199”, 30 January 2014.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2014/prt0199_30_01_2014.html

See also Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Diretrizes para Atenção Integral às Pessoas com Doenças Raras no Sistema Único de Saúde - SUS”, 2014.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/diretrizes_atencao_integral_pessoa_doencas_raras_SUS.pdf

³⁰ See for instance Löwy, Ilana, “Visible Disasters: Fetopathology in Brazil”, *Tangled Diagnoses: Prenatal Testing, Women, and Risk*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London, 2018, pp. 116: “There are no official data on the number of genetic tests offered in Brazil and their geographic distribution.” See also Horovitz, Dafne Dain Gandelman; Marques-de-Faria, Antonia Paula; Ferraz, Victor Evangelista de Faria, “The practice of medical genetics in Brazil”, in Kumar, Dhavendra (ed.), *Genomics and Health in the Developing World*. Oxford University Press, 2012, pp. 1224: “There are no official data on the number of genetic tests offered in Brazil and their geographic distribution.”

certain circumstances. A government Bill from 2013 proposes to offer women, who have a family history of cancer, tests to detect the mutation of the *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes:

VI - the examination of Genetic Mutation Detection of the *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes in women with a family history of cancer diagnosis of breast or ovary and that fit in clinical protocol of the Ministry of Health.

2. The clinical protocol provided for in item VI shall be reassessed at least once every two years in order to adapt to existing technical expertise, and should to establish all the prophylactic therapeutic possibilities for the cases detected in the gene mutation of the *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes.³¹

As of September 2018, this Bill has not been enacted into law. On the other hand, some states (i.e. some units of the Brazilian federation of states) enacted similar laws, which are valid only within these states. The state of Bahia, for instance, introduced free genetic testing for the mutation of the *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes in 2013.³² The state of Rio de Janeiro, the capital city of which is the city of Rio de Janeiro, introduced a similar law in 2015.³³ In the state of Rio de Janeiro the law was officially named “Angelina Jolie Law”, as an allusion to the American actress who opted for a mastectomy after a genetic test indicated that she had higher risk of developing breast cancer.³⁴ In 2007, a new bill was proposed to offer genetic counseling (*Port.: aconselhamento genético*) to prospective parents.³⁵ According to the Bill, prospective parents should have the right to know the probability a couple has to generate a child with some kind of inherited disorder. However, some segments of the society have criticized the Bill as a form of state sponsored eugenics (see remark on the use of the word “eugenics” in Portuguese at the end of this section). Some segments of the scientific community have also complained that, while the new Bill proposes that only geneticists would be entitled to require genetic tests from prospective parents, every physician should be allowed to

³¹ Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 6262”, 12 September 2013.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao;jsessionid=1DD9D9A22918DDE3711C1E4078D7878B.node2?idProposicao=590549&ord=0>

³² G1 GLOBO, “Exame que detecta chance de câncer pode ser feito pelo SUS em Salvador”, 15 May 2013.

<http://g1.globo.com/bahia/noticia/2013/05/exame-que-detecta-chance-de-cancer-pode-ser-feito-pelo-sus-em-salvador.html>

³³ Rio de Janeiro (Assembléia Legislativa do Rio de Janeiro), “Lei No. 7049”, 25 August 2015.

<http://alerjln1.alerj.rj.gov.br/CONTLEI.NSF/e9589b9aabd9cac8032564fe0065abb4/b598c5bdbbe2dccc83257ead006ff9fe?OpenDocument>

³⁴ G1 GLOBO, “RJ aprova lei ‘Angelina Jolie’ para dar exame a mulher com câncer na família”, 28 August 2015.

<http://g1.globo.com/rio-de-janeiro/noticia/2015/08/rj-aprova-lei-angelina-jolie-para-dar-exame-mulher-com-cancer-na-familia.html> See also Marinelli, Isabella, “Aprovada a Lei Angelina Jolie: Medida autoriza teste genético gratuito para prevenir câncer de mama”, *Revista Claudia*, 28 August 2015.

<https://claudia.abril.com.br/saude/aprovada-a-lei-angelina-jolie-medida-autoriza-teste-genetico-gratuito-para-prevenir-cancer-de-mama/>

³⁵ Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 1971”, 17 September 2007.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=366398>

prescribe a genetic test. Questions relative to informed consent as far as the new Bill is concerned have not yet been publicly debated.³⁶ As of September 2018, this Bill has not been enacted into law.

The private sector offers a wider range of genetic tests. These tests must ultimately comply with the Biosecurity Law, with the Consumer Protection Code (*Port.: Código de Defesa do Consumidor*, Law No. 8.078, from 11 September 1990)³⁷, with The Brazilian Civil Code (Brazilian private law main statute) (*Port.: Código Civil*, Law No. 10.406, from 10 January 2002),³⁸ and with CFM Resolution No. 2.168-2017.³⁹

The word “eugenics” (*Port.: eugenia*) has a derogatory connotation in Portuguese as Brazil pursued “eugenic policies” in the first half of twentieth century in the attempt to increase the number of white people in the population.⁴⁰ For this reason, the word “eugenics” is still associated with the deliberate attempt to change the phenotypic profile of the population so as to favor human features

³⁶ Raskin, Salmo, “Exame genético pré-nupcial: O Brasil está pronto para oferecer?” *Veja*, 9 March 2018. <https://veja.abril.com.br/blog/letra-de-medico/exame-genetico-pre-nupcial-o-brasil-esta-pronto-para-oferecer/>

See also Portal Hospitais Brasil, “Ministério da Saúde planeja oferecer aconselhamento genético para prevenção de doenças hereditárias”, 20 March 2018.

<http://portalhospitaisbrasil.com.br/ministerio-da-saude-planeja-oferecer-aconselhamento-genetico-para-prevencao-de-doencas-hereditarias/>

See also Sociedade Brasileira de Genética Médica e Genômica, “Geneticistas contestam projeto que propõe teste pré-nupcial em casais proposto pelo Governo Federal”. <http://www.sbgm.org.br/noticias/geneticistas-contestam-projeto-que-propoe-teste-pre-nupcial-em-casais-proposto-pelo-governo-federal>

See also Polato, Amanda, “Aconselhamento Genético chega ao SUS, mas política enfrenta críticas”, *Revista Época*, 22 February 2014. <https://epoca.globo.com/vida/vida-util/saude-e-bem-estar/noticia/2014/02/baconselhamento-geneticob-chega-ao-sus-mas-nova-politica-enfrenta-criticas.html>

See also, EBC, “SUS deve oferecer o teste genético: A biomédica e embriologista, Carine de Lima, fala sobre as dúvidas geradas na gravidez” (podcast), August, 2017.

<http://radios.ebc.com.br/revista-brasil/2017/08/SUS-deve-oferecer-o-teste-genetico>

³⁷ Brasil, “Lei 8.078”, 11 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

³⁸ Brasil, “Código Civil Brasileiro, Lei No. 10.406”, 10 January 2002.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/l10406.htm.

³⁹ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No.2.168”, 10 November 2017.

<https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2168>

See also Mendes, Marcela Custodio and Ana Paula Pimentel Costa, “Diagnóstico genético pré-implantacional: prevenção, tratamento de doenças genéticas e aspectos ético-legais”, *Revista Ciências Médicas e Biológica*, Salvador, Vol. 12, n.3, September/December, 2013, pp. 374-379.

https://repositorio.ufba.br/ri/bitstream/ri/23102/1/17_v.12_3.pdf

See also Passos-Bueno, Maria Rita et al. “Genetics and genomics in Brazil: a promising future”, *Molecular Genetics & Genomic Medicine*, Vol. 2, No. 4, 2014, pp. 280-91.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4113268/>

⁴⁰ Stepan, Nancy Leys, “Eugenics in Brazil, 1917-1940”, in Mark B. Adams (ed.), *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia*, Oxford University Press, Oxford/New York, 1990, pp. 110-152. See also Hochman, Gilberto, and Nísia Trindade Lima, Macos Chor Maio, “The path of eugenics in Brazil: Dilemmas of miscegenation”, in Alison Bashford, Philippa Levine (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of the History of Eugenics*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2010, pp. 493-510. See also Walsh, Sarah, “The executioner’s shadow: Coerced sterilization and the creation of ‘Latin’ eugenics in Chile”, *History of Science*, pp. 1-23 (doi/10.1177/0073275318755533).

that some people (out of prejudice) consider better than other features (having white skin rather than black skin, having blue eyes rather than dark eyes, etc.). The use of the word “eugenics” as it has been employed, for instance, by Nicholas Agar in the 2004 book *Liberal eugenics: In defence of human enhancement*, is not current in the Portuguese language outside of the academic debate on human enhancement.⁴¹

10. Prenatal testing/screening

Prenatal care is regulated by a Law that came into force by means of Decree No. 569, from 1 July 2000.⁴² Currently, however, no genetic test is available in the list of prenatal tests offered by SUS, the public health care system. On the other hand, there is a government Bill that proposes to introduce pre-nuptial genetic testing in Brazil.⁴³ This law aims at couples who intend to initiate a pregnancy and want to know in advance if a child genetically related to them would be likely to have some genetic disorder. This law would not apply in the case of an ongoing pregnancy. As of September 2018, this Bill has not been enacted into law. It is important to notice, though, that some genetically related diseases, such as sickle cell disease and beta-thalassemia, may be tested for during prenatal care within the public health care system. The test is performed if the mother-to-be is afro-descendent, or if she has a family history of sickle cell disease or beta-thalassemia, or if she suffers from chronic anaemia.⁴⁴ Presence of sickle cell disease or beta-thalassemia is examined by means of a blood test called hemoglobin electrophoresis, which (to the best of our knowledge) does not qualify as a genetic test.

The private sector, on the other hand, offers a wider range of genetic tests for pregnant women, including the Non Invasive Prenatal Testing, or NIPT (*Port.: Teste Pré-Natal Não-Invasivo*, or NACE), which indicates whether the fetus has Down syndrome, Edwards syndrome, or Patau syndrome.⁴⁵

⁴¹ Agar, Nicholas, *Liberal eugenics: In defence of human enhancement*, Blackwell, Oxford, 2004.

⁴² Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 569”, 1 June 2000.

http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2000/prt0569_01_06_2000_rep.html

⁴³ Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 1971”, 17 September 2007.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=366398>

⁴⁴ Laboissière, Paula, “Ministério inclui exame que detecta anemia falciforme na lista de procedimentos pré-natais”, *Agência Brasil*, 8 March 2012.

<http://memoria.ebc.com.br/agenciabrasil/noticia/2012-03-08/ministerio-inclui-exame-que-detecta-anemia-falciforme-na-lista-de-procedimentos-pre-natais>

See also Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Ministério da Saúde lança manual para orientar tratamento de talassemia”, 11 May 2016.

<http://portalms.saude.gov.br/noticias/agencia-saude/23630-ministerio-da-saude-lanca-manual-para-orientar-tratamento-de-talassemia>

See also Lemos, Marcela, “Eletroforese de hemoglobina: o que é, como é feita e para que serve”, *Tua Saúde*, August 2018.

<https://www.tuasaude.com/eletroforese-de-hemoglobina/>

See also Telessaúde, “Para realizar o diagnóstico precoce de anemia falciforme, qual exame o casal poderia realizar para saber sobre a chance de seu filho nascer com a doença? Seria exame genético?” 22 May 2017.

<https://telessaude.prefeitura.sp.gov.br/para-realizar-o-diagnostico-precoce-de-anemia-falciforme-qual-exame-o-casal-poderia-realizar-para-saber-sobre-a-chance-de-seu-filho-nascer-com-a-doenca-seria-exame-genetico/>

⁴⁵ Igenomix, “Exame Pré-Natal Não Invasivo em Sangue Materno (NIPT). <https://nace.igenomix.com.br/>

Prenatal testing services available in the private sector must ultimately comply with the Biosecurity Law, with the Consumer Protection Code (*Port.: Código de Defesa do Consumidor*, Law No. 8.078, from 11 September 1990),⁴⁶ with the Brazilian Civil Code (Brazilian private law main statute) (*Port.: Código Civil*, Law No. 10.406, from 10 January 2002),⁴⁷ and with CFM Resolution n.2.168-2017, which regulates the use of IVF and PGD in Brazilian fertility clinics.⁴⁸

In spite of recent public campaigning for its legalization, abortion is still forbidden in Brazil.⁴⁹ There are, however, three circumstances in which abortion is considered legal, namely: when the pregnancy represents a threat to the life of the pregnant woman; when the pregnancy resulted from sexual violence; when the fetus is anencephalic.⁵⁰

11. Newborn screening

The National Newborn Screening Initiative (*Port.: Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal*, PNTN) was created by means of Decree No. 822, from 6 July 2001.⁵¹ The most important newborn screening test offered in the public health care system is the neonatal heel prick test (*Port.: teste do pezinho*). The heel prick test is mandatory in Brazil and, depending on the municipal legislation, a birth certificate will not be issued before the test has been performed. The following conditions are screened for in the heel prick test:

⁴⁶ Brasil, “Lei No. 8.078”, 11 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

⁴⁷ Brasil, “Código Civil Brasileiro, Lei No. 10.406”, 10 January 2002. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/l10406.htm

⁴⁸ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No. 2.168”, 10 November 2017. <https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2168>

See also Mendes, Marcela Custodio, and Ana Paula Pimentel Costa, “Diagnóstico genético pré-implantacional: prevenção, tratamento de doenças genéticas e aspectos etico-legais”, *Revista Ciências Médicas e Biológica*, Salvador, Vol. 12, No.3, September/December 2013, pp.374-379. https://repositorio.ufba.br/ri/bitstream/ri/23102/1/17_v.12_3.pdf

⁴⁹ Andreoni, Manuela, and Ernesto Londoño, “Brazil’s Supreme Court Considers Decriminalizing Abortion”, *The New York Times*, 3 August, 2018, <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/08/03/world/americas/brazil-abortion-supreme-court.html>

⁵⁰ Araujo, Marcelo de, “Síndrome de Down e sentimentos morais: O caso dos abortos na Europa e EUA”, *Estadão*, 19 September 2017. <https://cultura.estadao.com.br/blogs/estado-da-arte/sindrome-de-down-e-sentimentos-morais-o-caso-dos-abortos-na-europa-e-eua/>

⁵¹ Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 822”, 6 June 2001. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2001/prt0822_06_06_2001.html

See also Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Dados sobre o Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal” 28 June 2017. <http://portalms.saude.gov.br/acoes-e-programas/programa-nacional-da-triagem-neonatal/dados-sobre-o-programa-nacional-de-triagem-neonatal>

See also Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Manual de Normas Técnicas e Rotinas Operacionais do Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal”, 2002. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/triagem_neonatal.pdf

See also video Ministério da Saúde, “Veja como o teste do pezinho é realizado no SUS”, 11 October 2016. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VBpa-f-6-KE>

For other tests within the public health care system see Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), Exames da Triagem Neonatal. <http://portalms.saude.gov.br/saude-para-voce/saude-da-crianca/pre-natal-e-parto/exames-de-triagem-neonatal>.

- Hypothyroidism (Port.: *Hipotireoidismo congênito*)
- Phenylketonuria (Port.: *Fenilcetonúria*)
- Sick cell disease and other hemoglobinopathies (Port.: *Doença falciforme e outras hemoglobinopatias*)
- Cystic fibrosis (Port.: *Fibrose cística*)
- Biotin (Port.: *Deficiência de biotinidase*)
- Congenital adrenal hyperplasia (Port.: *Hiperplasia adrenal congenital*)

There is a Bill from 2015 that proposes to include other tests within the list of tests covered by the heel prick test.⁵² As of September 2018, this Bill has been enacted into law. Other newborn screening tests offered within the public health care system include Newborn Hearing Screening, as introduced by Decree (Port.: *Portaria*) No. 1.328, from 3 December 2012⁵³, and the assessment of heart condition and eyesight.⁵⁴

The private sector also offers a wide range of newborn genetic tests, which must ultimately comply with the Biosecurity Law, with the Consumer Protection Code (Port.: *Código de Defesa do Consumidor*, Law No. 8.078, from 11 September 1990)⁵⁵, with the Brazilian Civil Code (Brazilian private law main statute) (Port.: *Código Civil*, Law No. 10.406, from 10 January 2002).⁵⁶

12. Advertising of genetic testing or screening

Article 5 of the Biosecurity Law prohibits the commercialization of human cells in Brazil:

⁵² Brasil, “Teste do pezinho pode ser ampliado”, *Senado Federal Notícias*, 9 September 2015. <https://www12.senado.leg.br/noticias/materias/2015/09/09/teste-do-pezinho-pode-ser-ampliado>

See also Brasil (Senado Federal), “Projeto de Lei No. 48”, 2015.

<https://www25.senado.leg.br/web/atividade/materias/-/materia/119759>

See also Brasil “Projeto de Lei 6771”, 24 August 2017.

http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/prop_mostrarintegra?codteor=1519297

⁵³ Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 1.328”, 3 December 2012.

http://bvsm.s.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/sas/2012/prt1328_03_12_2012.html

See also Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Diretrizes da Atenção à Triagem Auditiva Neonatal”, 2012.

http://bvsm.s.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/diretrizes_atencao_triagem_auditiva_neonatal.pdf

⁵⁴ Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Exames da Triagem Neonatal”. <http://portals.saude.gov.br/saude-para-voce/saude-da-crianca/pre-natal-e-parto/exames-de-triagem-neonatal>

See also Leão, Letícia Lima and Marcos José Aguiar, “Triagem neonatal: o que os pediatras deveriam saber”, *J. Pediatr. (Rio J.)*, Vol. 84, No. 4, 2008, pp. S80-S90. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0021-75572008000500012>

⁵⁵ Brasil, “Lei No. 8.078”, 11 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

⁵⁶ Brasil, “Código Civil Brasileiro. Lei No. 10.406”, 10 January 2002.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/l10406.htm.

Paragraph 3 - The commercialization of the biological material referred to in this article is prohibited and its practice implies the crime typified in art. 15 of Law No. 9.434 of February 4, 1997.⁵⁷

On the other hand, Brazilian legislation does not prohibit the importation of human semen for use in fertility clinics. This means that a man cannot sell a sample of his own semen to a sperm bank in Brazil. Yet, prospective parents are not forbidden to go online and order a vial of semen from a sperm bank abroad, and have it sent to a fertility clinic in Brazil. Fertility clinics, genetic counselling, and genetic tests are widely available in the private sector.

Examples of private clinics for genetic testing or genetic counselling in Brazil

- Genera: Inovação em Saúde: <https://www.genera.com.br>
- Gene Laboratório: <http://www.laboratorigene.com.br>
- Genomika: <https://www.genomika.com.br>
- Testes genéticos: <https://www.testesgeneticos.com.br>
- Gene One: <http://www.geneone.com.br>
- Freury Medicina e Saúde: <https://www.fleurygenomica.com.br>
- Nace: <https://nace.igenomix.com.br>
- Cell Preserve: <https://www.cellpreserve.com.br/exames-geneticos>

Examples of private fertility clinics in Brazil

- Centro de Fertilidade Vida: <http://vidafertil.com.br>
- Gera: Restauração da Fertilidade: <https://clinicagera.com.br>
- Origen: <https://origen.com.br>
- Huntington: <http://www.huntington.com.br>
- Mater Prime: Clínica de Reprodução Humana: <http://www.materprime.com.br>
- Pró Nascer: Reprodução Humana: <http://www.pronascer.com.br/index.html>
- Fertilidade: <https://fertilidade.org>
- Vida Bem Vinda - Clínica de Reprodução Humana: <http://www.vidabemvinda.com.br>

⁵⁷ Article 15 of Law No. 9.434, from 4 February 1997 states the following “Buying or selling tissues, organs or parts of the human body: Penalty - imprisonment, from three to eight years, and fine, from 200 to 360 days-fine.” Available at http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/LEIS/L9434.htm.

- Pró Criar: Medicina Reprodutiva: <https://www.procriar.com.br>

Fertility clinics, genetic counselling, and genetic tests offered in the private sector must ultimately comply with the Biosecurity Law, with the Consumer Protection Code (*Port.: Código de Defesa do Consumidor*, Law No. 8.078, from 11 September 1990)⁵⁸, with The Brazilian Civil Code (*Port.: Código Civil*, Law No. 10.406, from 10 January 2002),⁵⁹ and with CFM Resolution n.2.168-2017.⁶⁰

There is currently a growing demand for foreign human semen, imported from sperm banks abroad, for the purpose of assisted human reproduction in Brazilian fertility clinics. According to a report published by ANVISA in 2017, the importation of sperm samples for assisted human reproduction increased 2.625% in Brazil between 2011 and 2016.⁶¹ The demand is so high that the American sperm bank Fairfax Cryobank set up a website in Portuguese for its Brazilian clients.⁶² Many American sperm banks enable prospective clients to choose from a variety of features attributed to the anonymous sperm donor, including, for instance, his highest academic degree, which appears under the label “Education” in the search engine of Fairfax Cryobank’s website. Whether or not this option increases the odds of having a child with above average intelligence is a disputable question, even recognizing that there is strong evidence for the heritability of intelligence.⁶³

The CFM Resolution No. 2.168/2017 forbids the use of IVF and PGD techniques for non-therapeutic purposes (Part 1, §2, 5 and 6):

⁵⁸ Brasil, “Lei No. 8.078”, 11 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

⁵⁹ Brasil, “Código Civil Brasileiro, Lei No. 10.406”, 10 January 2002. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/l10406.htm

⁶⁰ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No.2.168”, 10 November 2017. <https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2168>

See also Mendes, Marcela Custodio, and Ana Paula Pimentel Costa, “Diagnóstico genético pré-implantacional: Prevenção, tratamento de doenças genéticas e aspectos etico-legais”, *Revista Ciências Médicas e Biológica*, Vol. 12, No.3, September/December, 2013, pp. 374-379.

https://repositorio.ufba.br/ri/bitstream/ri/23102/1/17_v.12_3.pdf

⁶¹ Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “1º Relatório de Amostras Seminais para uso em Reprodução Humana Assistida”, Brasília, 2017.

<http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/documents/4048533/4993603/1%C2%B0+Relat%C3%B3rio+de+Importa%C3%A7%C3%A3o+de+Amostras+Seminais.pdf/Ofa75253-6c73-4b7b-be0c-898f03ccace6>

⁶² Fairfax Cryobank. <https://fairfaxcryobank.com/br/>

See also Alves, Ana Beatriz, “Fertilização in vitro cresceu 149% nos últimos cinco anos no Brasil”, *Pais&Filhos*, 23 November 2017. <https://paisefilhos.uol.com.br/quero-engravidar/fertilizacao-in-vitro-cresceu-149-nos-ultimos-cinco-anos-no-brasil/>.

⁶³ Sniekers, S. et al., “Genome-wide association meta-analysis of 78,308 individuals identifies new loci and genes influencing human intelligence”, *Nature Genetics*, Vol. 49, 2017, pp. 1107-1112.

See also Nature. “Intelligence test: Modern genetics can rescue the study of intelligence from a history marred by racism”, Vol. 452, 25 May 2017, pp. 385-386; Shakeshaft, N. et al., “Thinking positively: The genetics of high intelligence”, *Intelligence*, Vol. 48, 123-132; Flynn, J., “Intelligence and human progress”, *The story of what was hidden in our genes*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2013. Plomin, R., “Commentary: Why are children in the same family so different? Non-shared environment three decades later”, *International Journal of Epidemiology*, Vol. 40, 2007, pp. 592-596. Deary, I. et al., “Genetics of intelligence”. *European Journal of Human Genetics*, Vol. 14, 2006, pp. 690-700; Ed, Y., “Chinese project probes the genetics of genius. Bid to unravel the secrets of brainpower faces skepticism”, *Nature*, Vol. 497, 2007, pp. 297-299; Allhoff, F., “Germ-line genetic enhancement and Rawlsian primary goods”. *Journal of Evolution and Technology*, Vol. 18 No. 1, 2008, pp. 23, note 7.

5. AR [sc. Assisted Reproduction] techniques cannot be applied with the intention of selecting the sex (presence or absence of Y chromosome) or any other biological feature of the future child, except to avoid possible descending diseases.⁶⁴

6. The fertilization of human oocytes for any purpose other than human procreation shall be prohibited.

It is worth mentioning, however, that although genetic human enhancement is forbidden in Brazil, the importation of human semen from sperm banks abroad, which enables prospective parents to choose for the highest degree of “Education” of a particular sperm donor as an indication of intelligence, is a clear example of pursuit of genetic cognitive enhancement in all but name.⁶⁵

13. Biobanks

The operation of biobanks for the purpose of storage of cord blood (*Port.: sangue de cordão*) and placental blood (*Port.: placentário*) are devised and regularly updated by ANVISA. Currently, biobanks have to comply with Resolution (*Port.: Resolução*) RDC No. 214, from 7 February 2018.⁶⁶ Brazilian government has also its own network of biobanks, called Rede BrasilCord⁶⁷, which was created by means of Decree (*Port.: Portaria*) No. 2.381, from 29 September 2004.⁶⁸ Rede BrasilCord aims mainly at the treatment of patients in need of a blood marrow transplant. Donation of cord blood and placental blood requires the informed consent from mothers.

Over the last few years, several private biobanks also started to operate in Brazil. Examples of private biobanks include:

- <http://hemocord.com.br/>
- <http://cryopraxis.com.br/>
- <http://bcubrasil.com.br/>
- <https://www.cellpreserve.com.br/celulas-tronco>

⁶⁴ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No.2.168”, 10 November 2017.
<https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2168>

⁶⁵ Araujo, Marcelo de, “Editing the genome of human beings CRISPR-Cas9 and the ethics of genetic enhancement”, *Journal of Evolution and Technology*, Vol. 27, n. 1, 2017, pp. 24-42.

⁶⁶ Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Resolução da Diretoria Colegiada - RDC No. 214”, 7 February 2018, <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/legislacao#/visualizar/367845>. See also Fundação Oswaldo Cruz, “Biobancos e biorrepositórios”, <https://portal.fiocruz.br/biobancos-e-biorrepositorios>

⁶⁷ Instituto Nacional do Câncer José de Alencar Gomes da Silva (INCA), “Registro nacional de doadores voluntários de medula óssea”, <http://redome.inca.gov.br/cordao-umbilical/rede-brasilcord/>
See also Instituto Nacional do Câncer José de Alencar Gomes da Silva (INCA), “Perguntas e respostas sobre sangue de cordão umbilical”. <http://www.blog.saude.gov.br/index.php/promocao-da-saude/51376-sangue-do-cordao-umbilical-pode-ser-doado-em-bancos-publicos>.

⁶⁸ Brasil (Ministério do Brasil), “Portaria No. 2.381”, 29 September 2004,
http://bvsm.sau.gov.br/bvs/saualegis/gm/2004/prt2381_29_10_2004.html
See also Instituto Nacional do Câncer José de Alencar Gomes da Silva (INCA), “Rede BrasilCord”,
http://www2.inca.gov.br/wps/wcm/connect/orientacoes/site/home/rede_brasilcord

- <https://ccb.med.br/>
- <https://www.cordvida.com.br/>

The crucial difference between the private and public biobanks is that in the private sector cord blood and placental blood are stored for possible use by the donor themselves, in case they need their own cells in the future. The public sector, on the other hand, benefits anyone who needs of a bone marrow transplant, even patients whose cells have been stored in private biobanks. Unlike public biobanks, which do not charge for their services, private biobanks are also very expensive. The main advantage of private biobanks is the expectation that, in the future, stem cells may be used to treat a wider range of conditions than the current stage of scientific development allows.

ANVISA has been campaigning for public's awareness of Rede BrasilCord over the last few years.⁶⁹ They try to convince more women to agree to donate the cord blood and placental blood of their newborn children so that more people are benefited from the services offered by Rede BrasilCord.⁷⁰

⁶⁹ Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), "Sangue do cordão umbilical e placentário", <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/sangue-de-cordao-umbilical-e-placentario>. See also Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), "Conhecendo os bancos de sangue de cordão umbilical e placentário", 2015. <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/documents/4048533/4993603/Conhecendo+os+Bancos+de+Sangue+de+Cord%C3%A3o+Umbilical+e+Placent%C3%A1rio/f0f9b587-8043-44c4-9d24-105f15ee2749>

⁷⁰ G1 GLOBO, "Bancos de cordão umbilical privados fizeram só 13 transplantes em 10 anos", 3 February 2015, <http://g1.globo.com/bemestar/noticia/2015/02/bancos-de-cordao-umbilical-privados-fizeram-so-13-transplantes-em-11-anos.html> See also Zebini, Daniela and Malu Echeverria, "Congelar o cordão umbilical vale a pena?", *G1 GLOBO*, 7 November 2017. <https://revistacrescer.globo.com/Voce-precisa-saber/noticia/2017/11/congelar-o-cordao-umbilical-vale-pena.html> For Legal Scholarship on Biobanks in Brazil see Pranke, Patricia, "A importância construir bancos de sangue de cordão umbilical no Brasil", *Ciência e Cultura*, Vol. 56 No. 3, São Paulo, July/Spetember, 2004, pp. 39-40. See also Garrido, Rodrigo Grazinoli, and Eduardo Leal Rodrigues, "O banco de perfis genéticos brasileiro três anos após a Lei no 12.654", *Rev. Bioética y Derecho*, No. 35, 2015, pp. 94-104. http://scielo.isciii.es/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1886-58872015000300009 http://cienciaecultura.bvs.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0009-67252004000300018 See also Mendes-Takao, Marília R. et al., "Bancos de sangue de cordão umbilical e placentário para uso familiar, de caráter privado, no Brasil: Subsídios técnicos, legais e éticos para uma análise de implementação". *Rev. Bras. Hematol. Hemoter.*, Vol. 32, No. 4, 2010, pp.317-328, http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?pid=S1516-84842010000400009&script=sci_abstract&tlng=pt. See also http://scielo.isciii.es/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1886-58872015000300009 See also Silva, Marinalva Oliveira, and Lélia Cristina Tenório Leoi, "Banco de Sangue de Cordão Umbilical e Placentário no Brasil", *Ensaios e Ciência: Ciências Biológicas, Agrárias e da Saúde*, V. 14, No. 2, 2010, pp. 125-141. <http://www.redalyc.org/pdf/260/26019017011.pdf> See also Cruz, L. E. and Jorge et al., "Sangue de cordão umbilical para uso autólogo ou grupo de pacientes especiais", *Revista Brasileira de Hematologia e Hemoterapia*. Vol. 31, suppl. 1., 2009, pp.36-44. <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rbhh/v31s1/aop2709>

Part IV Discussion and conclusions

14. Discussion

As a federation of states, Brazil allows its states and municipalities to issue their own norms in a variety of matters related to health, security, education, taxation, etc. In Brazil, the enormous inequality in wealth affects not only individual families, but also states and municipalities. While some states (or municipalities) offer a wider range of services, others lack resources to provide even basic sanitation. Moreover, some states (or municipalities) do not keep easily accessible record of the genetic tests performed under their jurisdiction. For this reason, as we have mentioned earlier, currently there is not a central data bank with updated information in this area. It is also worth mentioning that private hospitals and private providers of health services such as fertility clinics and genetic counselors play an important role in the Brazilian health system as a whole. But the private sector has also been a source of legal disputes, as patients often sue health insurance providers for failing to cover the costs of treatments or medicines. For this reason, Brazilian government created in 1998 a special regulatory body, subordinated to the Ministry of Medicine, responsible for establishing rules with which the health insurance providers have to comply, namely the National Agency of Supplementary Health (*Port.: Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar*, or ANS).⁷¹ In 2014, for instance, ANS issued a resolution according to which health insurance providers are compelled to cover the costs related to genetic tests for 29 diseases, including, for instance, the test to detect the mutation of the *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes.⁷² On the other hand, patients who do not have health policy insurances have to rely on the public health care system.

15. Conclusion

The Brazilian normative framework for the regulation of health services (both in the public and in the private sector) and for research related human genetics and human genomics involves a variety of legislation enacted by the federal government, by individual states of the federation, and by municipalities within the states. It also encompasses documents issued by government agencies that, strictly speaking, do not have legislative power, but whose decisions (referred to throughout the document as “resolutions”) are binding. Ultimately, all legal documents and all resolutions have to accord with the Constitution and, more specifically, with the Biosecurity Law.

⁷¹ Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar, <http://www.ans.gov.br/>

⁷² Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar, “ANS amplia cobertura obrigatória para 29 doenças genéticas”, 12 December 2013, <http://www.ans.gov.br/a-ans/sala-de-noticias-ans/consumidor/2316-ans-amplia-cobertura-obrigatoria-para-29-doencas-geneticas->

References

- Andreoni, Manuela, and Ernesto Londoño, “Brazil’s Supreme Court considers decriminalizing abortion”, *The New York Times*, 3 August, 2018, <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/08/03/world/americas/brazil-abortion-supreme-court.html>
- Agar, Nicholas, *Liberal eugenics: In defence of human enhancement*, Blackwell, Oxford, 2004.
- Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar: <http://www.ans.gov.br/>
- Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar, “ANS amplia cobertura obrigatória para 29 doenças genéticas”, 12 December 2013, <http://www.ans.gov.br/a-ans/sala-de-noticias-ans/consumidor/2316-ans-amplia-cobertura-obrigatoria-para-29-doencas-geneticas->
- Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “1º Relatório de Amostras Seminais para uso em Reprodução Humana Assistida”, Brasília, 2017. <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/documents/4048533/4993603/1%C2%B0+Relat%C3%B3rio+de+Importa%C3%A7%C3%A3o+de+Amostras+Seminais.pdf/0fa75253-6c73-4b7b-be0c-898f03ccace6>
- Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Conhecendo os bancos de sangue de cordão umbilical e placentário”, 2015. <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/documents/4048533/4993603/Conhecendo+os+Bancos+de+Sangue+de+Cord%C3%A3o+Umbilical+e+Placent%C3%A1rio/f0f9b587-8043-44c4-9d24-105f15ee2749>
- Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Guia para a Condução de Estudos Não Clínicos de Toxicologia e Segurança Farmacológica Necessários ao Desenvolvimento de Medicamentos - Versão 2 (Versão 1.1)”, 31 January 2013. http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/resultado-de-busca?p_p_id=101&p_p_lifecycle=0&p_p_state=maximized&p_p_mode=view&p_p_col_id=column-1&p_p_col_count=1&_101_struts_action=%2Fasset_publisher%2Fview_content&_101_assetEntryId=3274317&_101_type=document
- Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Guia para a Condução de Estudos Não Clínicos de Toxicologia e Segurança Farmacológica Necessários ao Desenvolvimento de Medicamentos - Versão 2 (Versão 1.1)”, 31 January 2013.
- Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Nota da Anvisa sobre o uso de animais em estudos pré-clínicos”, 24 January 2013. http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/noticias/-/asset_publisher/FXrpx9qY7FbU/content/nota-da-anvisa-sobre-o-uso-de-animais-em-estudos-pre-clinicos/219201/pop_up?inheritRedirect=false
- Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Regularização de Empresas: Medicamentos, Pesquisa Clínica”. <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/pesquisa-clinica>
- Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Resolução da Diretoria Colegiada - RDC No. 10”, 3 March 2015. http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/documents/10181/3503972/RDC_10_2015_.pdf/9ecdac85-1b8e-4f69-9a69-996de4386244

Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Resolução da Diretoria Colegiada - RDC No. 214”, 7 February 2018, <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/legislacao#/visualizar/367845>.

Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Sangue do cordão umbilical e placentário”, <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/sangue-de-cordao-umbilical-e-placentario>.

Allhoff, F., “Germ-line genetic enhancement and Rawlsian primary goods”. *Journal of Evolution and Technology*, Vol. 18 No. 1, 2008, pp. 23, note 7.

Alves, Ana Beatriz, “Fertilização in vitro cresceu 149% nos últimos cinco anos no Brasil”, *Pais&Filhos*, 23 November 2017. <https://paisefilhos.uol.com.br/quero-engravidar/fertilizacao-in-vitro-cresceu-149-nos-ultimos-cinco-anos-no-brasil/>.

Araujo, Marcelo de, “Editing the genome of human beings CRISPR-Cas9 and the ethics of genetic enhancement”, *Journal of Evolution and Technology*, Vol. 27, n. 1, 2017, pp. 24-42.

Araujo, Marcelo de, “Síndrome de Down e sentimentos morais: O caso dos abortos na Europa e EUA”, *Estadão*, 19 September 2017. <https://cultura.estadao.com.br/blogs/estado-da-arte/sindrome-de-down-e-sentimentos-morais-o-caso-dos-abortos-na-europa-e-eua/>

Brasil (Ministério da Ciência Tecnologia e Inovação, Comissão Técnica Nacional de Biossegurança, CNTBio): <http://ctnbio.mcti.gov.br>

Brasil (Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação). https://www.mctic.gov.br/mctic/opencms/perguntas_frequentes/Lei_do_Bem.html

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Dados sobre o Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal”, 28 June 2017. <http://portalms.saude.gov.br/acoes-e-programas/programa-nacional-da-triagem-neonatal/dados-sobre-o-programa-nacional-de-triagem-neonatal>

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Diretrizes da Atenção à Triagem Auditiva Neonatal”, 2012. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/diretrizes_atencao_triagem_auditiva_neonatal.pdf

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Diretrizes para Atenção Integral às Pessoas com Doenças Raras no Sistema Único de Saúde - SUS”, 2014. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/diretrizes_atencao_integral_pessoa_doencas_raras_SUS.pdf

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Exames da Triagem Neonatal”. <http://portalms.saude.gov.br/saude-para-voce/saude-da-crianca/pre-natal-e-parto/exames-de-triagem-neonatal>

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Manual de Normas Técnicas e Rotinas Operacionais do Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal”, 2002. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/triagem_neonatal.pdf

Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Ministério da Saúde lança manual para orientar tratamento de talassemia”, 11 May 2016. <http://portalms.saude.gov.br/noticias/agencia-saude/23630-ministerio-da-saude-lanca-manual-para-orientar-tratamento-de-talassemia>

- Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 1.328”, 3 December 2012. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/sas/2012/prt1328_03_12_2012.html
- Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 199”, 30 January 2014. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2014/prt0199_30_01_2014.html
- Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 2.380”, 28 October 2004. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2004/prt2380_28_10_2004.html
- Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 569”, 1 June 2000. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2000/prt0569_01_06_2000_rep.html
- Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 81”, 20 January 2009. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2009/prt0081_20_01_2009.html
- Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 822”, 6 June 2001. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2001/prt0822_06_06_2001.html
- Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), *Manual de Normas Técnicas e Rotinas Operacionais do Programa Nacional de Triagem Neonatal*, 2002. http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/triagem_neonatal.pdf
- Brasil, (Ministério da Saúde), Exames da Triagem Neonatal. <http://portalms.saude.gov.br/saude-para-voce/saude-da-crianca/pre-natal-e-parto/exames-de-triagem-neonatal>.
- Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Resolução Nº 466, 12 November 2012” <http://conselho.saude.gov.br/resolucoes/2012/Reso466.pdf>
- Brasil (Ministério do Brasil), “Portaria No. 2.381”, 29 September 2004, http://bvsmms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/gm/2004/prt2381_29_10_2004.html
- Brasil (Senado Federal), “Projeto de Lei No. 48”, 2015. <https://www25.senado.leg.br/web/atividade/materias/-/materia/119759>
- Brasil “Projeto de Lei 6771”, 24 August 2017. http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/prop_mostrarintegra?codteor=1519297
- Brasil, “Código Civil Brasileiro. Lei No. 10.406”, 10 January 2002. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/l10406.htm.
- Brasil, “Constituição da República Federative do Brasil”. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm
- Brasil, “Decreto No. 5.798”, 7 June 2006. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_Ato2004-2006/2006/Decreto/D5798.htm
- Brasil, “Decreto No. 6.899”, 15 July 2009. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_Ato2007-2010/2009/Decreto/D6899.htm
- Brasil, “Lei 8.078”, 11 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

Brasil, “Lei No. 11.105”, 24 March 2005. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_Ato2004-2006/2005/Lei/L11105.htm

Brasil, “Lei No. 11.196”, 21 November 2005. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2004-2006/2005/lei/l11196.htm

Brasil, “Lei No. 11.794”, 8 October 2008. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2007-2010/2008/lei/l11794.htm

Brasil, “Lei No. 8.078”, 11 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

Brasil, “Lei No. 8.078”, 11 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

Brasil, “Lei No. 8.078”, 11 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

Brasil, “Lei No. 8.080”, 19 September 1990. http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/L8080.htm

Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 1971”, 17 September 2007.
<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=366398>

Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 6262”, 12 September 2013.
<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao;jsessionid=1DD9D9A22918DDE3711C1E4078D7878B.node2?idProposicao=590549&ord=0>

Brasil, “Teste do pezinho pode ser ampliado”, *Senado Federal Notícias*, 9 September 2015.
<https://www12.senado.leg.br/noticias/materias/2015/09/09/teste-do-pezinho-pode-ser-ampliado>

Colussi, Joana, “Edição de Gene e DNA em plantas e animais pode revolucionar o campo”, *Campo e Lavoura*, 8 June 2018. <https://gauchazh.clicrbs.com.br/economia/campo-e-lavoura/noticia/2018/06/edicao-de-dna-em-plantas-e-animais-promete-revolucionar-o-campo-cji69j8my0etc01qo8vhjwe04.html>

Colussi, Joana, “Edição de gene e DNA em plantas e animais pode revolucionar o campo”, *Campo e Lavoura*, 8 June 2018. <https://gauchazh.clicrbs.com.br/economia/campo-e-lavoura/noticia/2018/06/edicao-de-dna-em-plantas-e-animais-promete-revolucionar-o-campo-cji69j8my0etc01qo8vhjwe04.html>

Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No.2.168”, 10 November 2017.
<https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2168>

Cruz, L. E. and Jorge et al., “Sangue de cordão umbilical para uso autólogo ou grupo de pacientes especiais”, *Revista Brasileira de Hematologia e Hemoterapia*. Vol. 31, suppl. 1., 2009, pp.36-44.
<http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rbhh/v31s1/aop2709>

Deary, I. et al., “Genetics of intelligence”. *European Journal of Human Genetics*, Vol. 14, 2006, pp. 690-700; Ed, Y., “Chinese project probes the genetics of genius. Bid to unravel the secrets of brainpower faces skepticism”, *Nature*, Vol. 497, 2007, pp. 297-299.

Dubbudu, Rakesh, “How much do various countries contribute to the UN Budget?”, *Factly*, 13 December 2016. <https://factly.in/united-nations-budget-contributions-by-member-countries/>

EBC, “SUS deve oferecer o teste genético: A biomédica e embriologista, Carine de Lima, fala sobre as dúvidas geradas na gravidez” (podcast), August, 2017. <http://radios.ebc.com.br/revista-brasil/2017/08/SUS-deve-oferecer-o-teste-genetico>

Fairfax Cryobank. <https://fairfaxcryobank.com/br/>

Fundação Oswaldo Cruz, “Biobancos e biorrepositórios”, <https://portal.fiocruz.br/biobancos-e-biorrepositorios>

Fundação Oswaldo Cruz, “Os sistemas de saúde pública brasileiro e inglês enfrentam dilemas no ano em que completam 30 e 70 anos”, *Centro de Estudos Estratégicos da Fiocruz*, 21 February 2018. <http://www.cee.fiocruz.br/?q=os-sistemas-de-saude-publica-brasileiro-e-ingles-enfrentam-dilemas-no-ano-em-que-completam-30-e-70-anos>

G1 GLOBO, “Bancos de cordão umbilical privados fizeram só 13 transplantes em 10 anos”, 3 February 2015, <http://g1.globo.com/bemestar/noticia/2015/02/bancos-de-cordao-umbilical-privados-fizeram-so-13-transplantes-em-11-anos.html>

G1 GLOBO, “Exame que detecta chance de câncer pode ser feito pelo SUS em Salvador”, 15 May 2013. <http://g1.globo.com/bahia/noticia/2013/05/exame-que-detecta-chance-de-cancer-pode-ser-feito-pelo-sus-em-salvador.html>

G1 GLOBO, “RJ aprova lei ‘Angelina Jolie’ para dar exame a mulher com câncer na família”, 28 August 2015. <http://g1.globo.com/rio-de-janeiro/noticia/2015/08/rj-aprova-lei-angelina-jolie-para-dar-exame-mulher-com-cancer-na-familia.html>

Garrido, Rodrigo Grazinoli, and Eduardo Leal Rodrigues, “O Banco de Perfis Genéticos Brasileiro Três Anos após a Lei no 12.654”, *Rev. Bioética y Derecho*, No. 35, 2015, pp. 94-104. http://scielo.isciii.es/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1886-58872015000300009

Ghente, “Documentos jurídicos”, http://www.ghente.org/doc_juridicos/

Hochman, Gilberto, and Nísia Trindade Lima, Macos Chor Maio, “The path of eugenics in Brazil: Dilemmas of miscegenation”, in Alison Bashford, Philippa Levine (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of the History of Eugenics*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2010, pp. 493-510.

Horovitz, Dafne Dain Gandelman; Marques-de-Faria, Antonia Paula; Ferraz, Victor Evangelista de Faria, “The practice of medical genetics in Brazil”, in Kumar, Dhavendra (ed.), *Genomics and Health in the Developing World*. Oxford University Press, 2012, pp. 1216-1230.

Igenomix, “Exame Pré-Natal Não Invasivo em Sangue Materno (NIPT). <https://nace.igenomix.com.br/>

Instituto Nacional do Câncer José de Alencar Gomes da Silva (INCA), “Registro nacional de doadores voluntários de medula óssea”, <http://redome.inca.gov.br/cordao-umbilical/rede-brasilcord/>

Instituto Nacional do Câncer José de Alencar Gomes da Silva (INCA), “Perguntas e respostas sobre sangue de cordão umbilical”. <http://www.blog.saude.gov.br/index.php/promocao-da-saude/51376-sangue-do-cordao-umbilical-pode-ser-doadado-em-bancos-publicos>.

Instituto Nacional do Câncer José de Alencar Gomes da Silva (INCA), “Rede BrasilCord”, http://www2.inca.gov.br/wps/wcm/connect/orientacoes/site/home/rede_brasilcord

Laboissière, Paula, “Ministério inclui exame que detecta anemia falciforme na lista de procedimentos pré-natais”, *Agência Brasil*, 8 March 2012. <http://memoria.ebc.com.br/agenciabrasil/noticia/2012-03-08/ministerio-inclui-exame-que-detecta-anemia-falciforme-na-lista-de-procedimentos-pre-natais>

Leão, Letícia Lima and Marcos José Aguiar, “Triagem neonatal: o que os pediatras deveriam saber”, *J. Pediatr.*, Vol. 84, No. 4, 2008, pp.S80-S90. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0021-75572008000500012>

Lemos, Marcela, “Eletroforese de hemoglobina: o que é, como é feita e para que serve”, *Tua Saúde*, August 2018. <https://www.tuasaude.com/eletroforese-de-hemoglobina/>

Löwy, Ilana, “Visible Disasters: Fetopathology in Brazil”, *Tangled Diagnoses: Prenatal Testing, Women, and Risk*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London, 2018, pp. 108-146.

Marinelli, Isabella, “Aprovada a Lei Angelina Jolie: Medida autoriza teste genético gratuito para prevenir câncer de mama”, *Revista Claudia*, 28 August 2015. <https://claudia.abril.com.br/saude/aprovada-a-lei-angelina-jolie-medida-autoriza-teste-genetico-gratuito-para-prevenir-cancer-de-mama/>

Martins, Helena, “Justiça autoriza empresa a comercializar *Aedes aegypti* modificado”, *Agência Brasil*, 23 March 2018. <http://agenciabrasil.ebc.com.br/pesquisa-e-inovacao/noticia/2018-03/justica-autoriza-empresa-comercializar-aedes-aegypti-modificado>.

Mendes, Marcela Custodio, and Ana Paula Pimentel Costa, “Diagnóstico genético pré-implantacional: Prevenção, tratamento de doenças genéticas e aspectos etico-legais”, *Revista Ciências Médicas e Biológica*, Vol. 12, No.3, September/December, 2013, pp. 374-379. https://repositorio.ufba.br/ri/bitstream/ri/23102/1/17_v.12_3.pdf

Mendes-Takao, Marília R. et al., “Bancos de sangue de cordão umbilical e placentário para uso familiar, de caráter privado, no Brasil: Subsídios técnicos, legais e éticos para uma análise de implementação”. *Rev. Bras. Hematol. Hemoter.*, Vol. 32, No. 4, 2010, pp.317-328. http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?pid=S1516-84842010000400009&script=sci_abstract&tlng=pt.

Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, “Bem-estar deve reger a experimentação animal, afirma coordenadora do CONCEA”, 14 August 2018. <https://www.mctic.gov.br/mctic/opencms/institucional/concea/index.html>

Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, Legislação do CONCEA, “Lei 11.794”, 8 October 2008. <https://www.mctic.gov.br/mctic/opencms/institucional/concea/paginas/legislacao.html>

Moraes, Fernando Tadeu, “Justiça autoriza Oxitec a comercializar mosquito transgênico”, *Folha de São Paulo*, 26 March 2018. <https://www1.folha.uol.com.br/ciencia/2018/03/justica-autoriza-oxitec-a-comercializar-mosquito-transgenico.shtml>.

Nature, “Intelligence test: Modern genetics can rescue the study of intelligence from a history marred by racism”, *Nature*, Vol. 452, 25 May 2017, pp. 385-386.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). “Frascati Manual”.
<http://www.oecd.org/innovation/inno/frascati-manual.htm>.

Organization of American States (OAS), “Inter-American Convention against All Forms of Discrimination and Intolerance”, *Department of International Law (DIL)*, 2013.
http://www.oas.org/en/sla/dil/inter_american_treaties_A-69_discrimination_intolerance.asp

OXITEC. <http://br.oxitec.com/>

Passos-Bueno, Maria Rita et al. “Genetics and genomics in Brazil: a promising future”, *Molecular Genetics & Genomic Medicine*, Vol. 2, No. 4, 2014, pp. 280-91.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4113268/>

Plomin, R., “Commentary: Why are children in the same family so different? Non-shared environment three decades later”, *International Journal of Epidemiology*, Vol. 40, 2007, pp. 592-596.

Polato, Amanda, “Aconselhamento Genético chega ao SUS, mas política enfrenta críticas”, *Revista Época*, 22 February 2014. <https://epoca.globo.com/vida/vida-util/saude-e-bem-estar/noticia/2014/02/baconselhamento-geneticob-chega-ao-sus-mas-nova-politica-enfrenta-criticas.html>

Portal Hospitais Brasil, “Ministério da Saúde planeja oferecer aconselhamento genético para prevenção de doenças hereditárias”, 20 March 2018. <http://portalhospitaisbrasil.com.br/ministerio-da-saude-planeja-oferecer-aconselhamento-genetico-para-prevencao-de-doencas-hereditarias/>

Pranke, Patricia, “A importância construir bancos de sangue de cordão umbilical no Brasil”, *Ciência e Cultura*, Vol. 56 No. 3, São Paulo, July/Spetember, 2004, pp. 39-40.
http://cienciaecultura.bvs.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0009-67252004000300018

Raskin, Salmo, “Exame genético pré-nupcial: O Brasil está pronto para oferecer?” *Veja*, 9 March 2018. <https://veja.abril.com.br/blog/letra-de-medico/exame-genetico-pre-nupcial-o-brasil-esta-pronto-para-oferecer/>

Reuters, “Brazil is seeking to join the OECD despite its political crisis”, *Fortune*, 31 May 2017.
<http://fortune.com/2017/05/30/brazil-oecd-membership-temer/>

Rio de Janeiro (Assembléia Legislativa do Rio de Janeiro), “Lei No. 7049”, 25 August 2015.
<http://alerjln1.alerj.rj.gov.br/CONTLEI.NSF/e9589b9aabd9cac8032564fe0065abb4/b598c5bdbbe2dc83257ead006ff9fe?OpenDocument>

Servick, Kelly, “Brazil will release billions of lab-grown mosquitoes to combat infectious disease. Will it work?”, *Science*, 13 October 2016. <http://www.sciencemag.org/news/2016/10/brazil-will-release-billions-lab-grown-mosquitoes-combat-infectious-disease-will-it>

Shakeshaft, N. et al., “Thinking positively: The genetics of high intelligence”, *Intelligence*, Vol. 48, 123-132; Flynn, J., “Intelligence and human progress”, *The story of what was hidden in our genes*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2013.

Silva, Marinalva Oliveira, and Lélia Cristina Tenório Leoi, “Banco de Sangue de Cordão Umbilical e Placentário no Brasil”, *Ensaios e Ciência: Ciências Biológicas, Agrárias e da Saúde*, V. 14, No. 2, 2010, pp. 125-141. <http://www.redalyc.org/pdf/260/26019017011.pdf>

Silveira, Evanildo, “Os genes do gado”, *Pesquisa FAPESP*, April 2017. <http://revistapesquisa.fapesp.br/2017/04/19/os-genes-do-gado/>

Sniekers, S. et al., “Genome-wide association meta-analysis of 78,308 individuals identifies new loci and genes influencing human intelligence”, *Nature Genetics*, Vol. 49, 2017, pp. 1107-1112.

Sociedade Brasileira de Genética Médica e Genômica, “Geneticistas contestam projeto que propõe teste pré-nupcial em casais proposto pelo Governo Federal”. <http://www.sbgm.org.br/noticias/geneticistas-contestam-projeto-que-propoe-teste-pre-nupcial-em-casais-proposto-pelo-governo-federal>

Stepan, Nancy Leys, “Eugenics in Brazil, 1917-1940”, in Mark B. Adams (ed.), *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia*, Oxford University Press, Oxford/New York, 1990, pp. 110-152.

Tanaka, Oswaldo Yoshimi and Vanessa Elias de Oliveira, “Reforma(s) e Estruturação do Sistema de Saúde Britânico: lições para o SUS”, *Saúde e Sociedade*, Vol. 16, No. 1, April 2007, pp. 7-17. <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/sausoc/v16n1/02.pdf>.

Telessaúde, “Para realizar o diagnóstico precoce de anemia falciforme, qual exame o casal poderia realizar para saber sobre a chance de seu filho nascer com a doença? Seria exame genético?” 22 May 2017. <https://telessaude.prefeitura.sp.gov.br/para-realizar-o-diagnostico-precoce-de-anemia-falciforme-qual-exame-o-casal-poderia-realizar-para-saber-sobre-a-chance-de-seu-filho-nascer-com-a-doenca-seria-exame-genetico/>

UNESCO, “International Declaration on Human Genetic Data”, 16 October 2003. <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genetic-data/>

UNESCO, “Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights”, 11 November 1997. <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genome-and-human-rights/>

United Nation, “General assembly adopts United Nations Declaration on Human Cloning by vote of 84-34-37”, *Press Release*, 8 March 2005. <https://www.un.org/press/en/2005/ga10333.doc.htm>

Walsh, Sarah, “The executioner’s shadow: Coerced sterilization and the creation of ‘Latin’ eugenics in Chile”, *History of Science*, pp. 1-23 (doi/10.1177/0073275318755533).

Zebini, Daniela and Malu Echeverria, “Congelar o cordão umbilical vale a pena?”, *G1 GLOBO*, 7 November 2017. <https://revistacrescer.globo.com/Voce-precisa-saber/noticia/2017/11/congelar-o-cordao-umbilical-vale-pena.html>